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Effect Of Monetary Policy Instruments On Inflation In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria from 1993 to 2024. It specifically assessed the impact of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LR), and Open Market Operations (OMO) on the inflation rate using a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model. Time series econometric techniques, including unit root tests, Johansen co-integration, Granger causality analysis, impulse response functions, and variance decomposition, were employed. The short-run VAR estimates revealed that none of the monetary policy instruments had a statistically significant effect on inflation, indicating a weak and ineffective transmission mechanism. However, the Johansen co-integration test established a significant long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables, suggesting that monetary policy instruments and inflation move together over extended periods. The short-run ineffectiveness was attributed to structural and institutional weaknesses in the Nigerian economy, including high levels of informality, excess liquidity, shallow financial markets, and fiscal dominance. The study concluded that while a long-run relationship exists, inflation in Nigeria is predominantly driven by non-monetary factors in the short to medium term. It recommended that policymakers adopt a more integrated approach, combining monetary measures with structural reforms in agriculture, infrastructure, and public finance to ensure sustainable inflation control and macroeconomic stability..

Keywords: Monetary Policy Instruments, Inflation, VAR, Nigeria, MPR, CRR, OMO.

INTRODUCTION

Inflation remains one of the most significant macroeconomic challenges facing Nigeria. It has persisted as a critical issue, particularly between 2023 and 2024, driven by factors such as high food prices, currency depreciation, and global supply chain disruptions. By October 2024, inflation had reached 33.88%, reflecting ongoing price pressures that have severely affected the purchasing power of Nigerians (Leadership, 2024). In response, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has implemented several strategies to curb inflation, including raising the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) to 27.50% to reduce liquidity and control demand-driven inflation (CBN, 2024; Leadership, 2024). Additionally, the CBN has adopted an inflation-targeting framework, focusing on improving agricultural productivity and easing global supply chain constraints, with the aim of reducing inflation to 21.4% by mid-2024 (CBN, 2024; Leadership, 2024). These efforts, coupled with reforms in the foreign exchange market and enhanced fiscal coordination, are expected to help stabilize prices and support economic recovery (CBN, 2024).

Monetary policy is a crucial tool utilized by central banks worldwide to stabilize prices and manage economic growth. Globally, central banks such as the Federal Reserve in the United States, the European

Central Bank, and the Bank of Japan use various monetary policy instruments to influence inflation and economic conditions. These instruments include the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LRR), and Open Market Operations (OMO). The effectiveness of these tools is widely acknowledged as essential for maintaining low and stable inflation, which is a cornerstone of economic stability and growth (Mishkin, 2016; Taylor, 2000). Central banks adjust interest rates, manage reserve requirements, and conduct open market transactions to influence money supply and aggregate demand, aiming to achieve price stability and support broader economic objectives (Egbetunde, 2010).

Economies in developing regions, ranging from resource-rich nations like Nigeria to smaller, less developed countries, face unique challenges in implementing effective monetary policy. The African Development Bank (2019) highlights that institutional capacities and economic structures profoundly influence how monetary policy impacts inflation. While some countries have successfully used monetary policy to stabilize their economies, others struggle with the effectiveness of these measures due to factors such as weak institutional frameworks and external economic shocks (IMF, 2019; OECD, 2020).

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) employs a range of monetary policy tools to manage inflation and foster economic stability. The CBN utilizes the MPR, CRR, LRR, and OMO to regulate the money supply and influence inflation rates. The MPR, for instance, directly affects interest rates and borrowing costs, while the CRR and LRR influence the liquidity available to banks. OMO involves the buying and selling of government securities to control the money supply and manage inflation (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2020). Despite these efforts, Nigeria has faced persistent inflationary pressures, exacerbated by factors such as supply chain disruptions and food insecurity (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

The impact of these monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria has been mixed. While the CBN has managed to bring inflation rates down from double digits to single digits at various times, inflationary challenges persist (Egbetunde, 2010). Structural issues such as inadequate infrastructure and agricultural inefficiencies contribute to ongoing inflationary pressures that monetary policy alone cannot fully address (World Bank, 2020).

Inflation occurs when there is a general and continuous rise in the prices of goods and services in an economy (Fischer, 1993). A major cost is related to the inefficient utilization of resources because economic agents mistake changes in nominal variables for changes in real variables and act accordingly (Lucas, 1972). During inflationary periods, the opportunity cost of holding money increases, causing an inefficient use of real resources in transactions (Friedman, 1969). Therefore, inflation weakens the purchasing power of money and lowers the standard of living (Keynes, 1936). Policymakers have tried to adopt appropriate policies to combat inflation and ensure price stability (Taylor, 2000). Generally, the level of money supply and the stock of goods and services are two crucial factors that determine the level of inflation in an economy (Monetary Policy Committee, 2004). When inflation becomes persistent, these two factors become the primary targets of policies (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2005). An excess or shortage in the supply of money could either induce excess aggregate demand, resulting in a higher inflation rate, or induce stagnation, thus retarding economic growth and development (Friedman, 1968). While fiscal policy can help combat inflationary pressure, monetary policy has been the principal tool often employed by central banks to ensure price stability (Romer, 2006). While it is undeniable that monetary authorities have formulated various policy measures in an attempt to curb inflation, the effectiveness of these policies is questionable, as most economies, particularly developing ones, still experience inflationary challenges (Egbetunde, 2010).

For years, the Nigerian economy has faced socio-economic stagnation traceable to an inflationary spiral, particularly in the 1970s when inflation increased to double digits (Central Bank of Nigeria, 1980). The analysis of non-core inflation in the early 1990s reveals an inflation rate of 63.6% in late 1994 (National Bureau of Statistics, 1995). Headline inflation rose rapidly by 1995 to reach an all-time high of 72.8%, though it decelerated gradually to a single digit in 1997 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 1998). Similarly, core inflation, which began a gradual ascent in the early 1990s, peaked at about 69.0% in mid-1995 before slowing down in 1997 (National Bureau of Statistics, 1998). Since then, inflation remained at single digits between 1998 and 2001 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2002).

In 2003, macroeconomic stability was restored, following the gains of a comprehensive and consistent economic reform program (National Bureau of Statistics, 2004). However, the low inflation regime did not last long, with the resurgence of spikes in headline and core inflation between 2000 and 2001 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2005). The headline inflation rate remained in double digits between 2002 and 2005, recording 12.9%, 14%, 15%, and 17.9% in the respective years (National Bureau of Statistics, 2006). However, it decelerated dramatically to 8.24% and 5.38% in 2006 and 2007, before rising astronomically to 11.60% and 12.00% in 2008 and 2009, respectively. It then fell marginally to 11.8% in 2010 and 12.3% in 2013 (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2014).

Monetary policy instruments are the direct means available to the monetary authorities for influencing intermediate variables to achieve the ultimate goals of policy (Mishkin, 2016). These instruments are of two types: first, quantitative, general, or indirect market-based instruments; and second, qualitative, selective, or direct control instruments (Blanchard, 2017). The direct control instruments are discretionally manipulated to achieve set targets, while the market-based instruments are employed in a well-developed financial system to influence market participants in a way that achieves desirable targets (Taylor, 2000).

This study, therefore, examines the effectiveness of monetary policy instruments in controlling inflation in Nigeria, providing empirical insights to inform policymakers on optimal inflation management strategies.

Statement of the Problem

Monetary policy instruments, such as the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LRR), and Open Market Operations (OMO), are central to the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) strategy for managing inflation and fostering economic stability (Mishkin, 2016; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2020). Despite the strategic deployment of these instruments, inflation in Nigeria has exhibited significant volatility, fluctuating between high double digits and lower single digits over recent decades (Egbetunde, 2010). This volatility raises critical questions about the effectiveness of these monetary policy tools in stabilizing inflation and promoting sustainable economic growth.

The MPR influences interest rates and borrowing costs, CRR and LRR affect bank liquidity, and OMO controls the money supply through the buying and selling of government securities (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2020). However, the interaction between these instruments and their actual impact on inflation is not fully understood, particularly in the context of Nigeria's unique economic challenges.

The effectiveness of these instruments is further complicated by structural issues such as inadequate infrastructure, supply chain disruptions, and food insecurity, which can overshadow or distort the intended effects of monetary policy (IMF, 2019; National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). These challenges suggest that the relationship between monetary policy instruments and inflation in Nigeria is complex and multifaceted.

Despite the CBN's persistent use of monetary policy instruments to combat inflation, price instability remains a critical challenge, with inflation reaching 33.88% in 2024 (Leadership, 2024; CBN, 2024). While existing studies (Egbetunde, 2010; Mishkin, 2016) acknowledge the role of these tools in stabilizing economies, their effectiveness in Nigeria's unique context marked by structural bottlenecks, food supply shocks, and exchange rate volatility remains unclear (IMF, 2019; World Bank, 2020). Furthermore, conflicting findings in prior research (CBN, 2020; OECD, 2020) suggest a gap in understanding whether these instruments function optimally or require recalibration to address Nigeria's persistent inflationary pressures, necessitating an updated empirical assessment of their impact.

Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) on inflation in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) on inflation in Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effect of the Liquidity Reserve Ratio (LRR) on inflation in Nigeria?
- iv. What is the effect of Open Market Operations (OMO) on inflation in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Determine the effect of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the effect of the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- iii. Examine the effect of the Liquidity Reserve Ratio (LRR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- iv. Evaluate the effect of Open Market Operations (OMO) on inflation in Nigeria.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant effect of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant effect of the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- iii. There is no significant effect of the Liquidity Reserve Ratio (LRR) on inflation in Nigeria.
- iv. There is no significant effect of Open Market Operations (OMO) on inflation in Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

The study examined the effect of monetary instruments on inflation in Nigeria in the period of 1993 to 2024. The choice of this period is necessitated by various factors. First, both positive and negative effects of monetary policy have been observed especially in the period before the Structural Adjustment Programme. During this period, direct control measures were used to regulate the money supply in the country. This therefore resulted in a lot of malfunctioning in the economy. Also, indirect controls were put in place by the Central Bank. Till date, both the direct and indirect controls are in use by the Central Bank to control the price level in the economy.

The choice of the above period is also necessitated by the availability of data for the research work. The study will be limited to the following (Monetary policy Rate, Cash Reserve Ratio, Liquidity Reserve Ratio and Open Market Operation) because of the belief that the institution of various monetary policy instruments is meant to change the volume and value of money supply.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review:

Monetary Policy

Monetary policy refers to the actions undertaken by a central bank, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), to influence the availability and cost of money and credit to help promote national economic goals." (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). These actions, which include setting interest rates and managing reserve requirements, are primarily aimed at achieving price stability (low and stable inflation) as a prerequisite for sustainable economic growth and employment.

Monetary Policy Rate (MPR)

Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) is "the rate at which the CBN lends to the commercial banks and serves as the benchmark rate which all other rates revolve." It is the primary tool used by the Central Bank of Nigeria to manage liquidity, influence inflation, and guide the direction of the economy. (Central Bank of Nigeria, Monetary Policy Committee Framework 2023).

Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR)

Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) is the portion of a bank's total deposit liabilities that it is mandated to hold as reserves in liquid cash with the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). By adjusting the CRR, the CBN directly controls the amount of lendable funds available to commercial banks, making it a crucial tool for managing liquidity and controlling inflation in the economy (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023).

Liquidity Ratio (LR)

Liquidity Ratio (LR) is a prudential requirement set by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) that mandates commercial banks to maintain a minimum percentage of their total deposit liabilities in liquid assets. These assets include cash, balances with the CBN, and government securities. The ratio ensures that banks can meet their short-term obligations without distress, and it is also used as a monetary policy tool to influence the credit creation capacity of the banking system (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023).

Empirical Review

Nuhu & Odiba (2021) examined the effects of monetary policy in combating inflation in Nigeria... The findings indicated that interest rate and exchange rate exerted a positive and significant effect on inflation in Nigeria both in the short run and long-run. However, monetary policy rate was not significant in

influencing inflation rate in the long-run but was found to be significant in the short-run. It was therefore concluded that while interest rate and exchange rate are potent tools of controlling inflation, monetary policy rate is not very effective in controlling inflationary pressure in Nigeria.

Chinaemerem & Akujuobi (2012) examined inflation targeting and monetary policy Instruments in Nigeria and Ghana using Vector Auto Regressive (VAR) Models... The study concluded that policy linkage between inflation and monetary policy instruments in Nigeria and Ghana is not strong in the short run. The study recommended amongst others that the monetary authorities must reduce the influence of inflationary expectations by pursuing more transparent policies.

Adebayo, John, Chinedu, Suleiman & Adetunji. (2023) conducted a comprehensive study on the impact of monetary policy on inflation in Nigeria, emphasizing the moderating effects of external factors such as exchange rates and global oil prices. Utilizing monthly data from 2000 to 2022, the researchers employed a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to explore the dynamic relationship between inflation and various monetary policy instruments, including the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR). The study found that exchange rate depreciation significantly contributed to inflationary pressures, undermining the efficacy of domestic monetary policy. Similarly, fluctuations in global oil prices directly impacted inflation, given Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil exports for foreign exchange earnings. The Impulse Response Function (IRF) analysis revealed that inflation in Nigeria was more responsive to exchange rate and oil price shocks than to adjustments in domestic policy tools. The study recommended enhanced coordination between monetary and fiscal policies to improve economic stability, suggesting that stabilizing the naira and diversifying the economy could mitigate the impact of external shocks. Strengthening institutional capacity and implementing policies to manage exchange rates, such as building foreign reserves and promoting non-oil exports, were also highlighted as crucial steps for improving monetary policy effectiveness in Nigeria. This empirical review underscores the importance of considering external economic factors when formulating monetary policy in developing economies like Nigeria.

Nuhu & Odiba (2021) examined the effects of monetary policy in combating inflation in Nigeria. The main objective of this study was to assess the effect of monetary policy instruments in curbing inflation in Nigeria. The study used annual time series data from 1986-2019 which were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. It used inflation rate as the dependent variable while money supply, monetary policy rate, exchange rate and government expenditure were used as the explanatory variables. The study employed Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model for its analysis. The findings indicated that interest rate and exchange rate exerted a positive and significant effect on inflation in Nigeria both in the short run and long-run. However, monetary policy rate was not significant in influencing inflation rate in the long-run but was found to be significant in the short-run. It was therefore concluded that while interest rate and exchange rate are potent tools of controlling inflation, monetary policy rate is not very effective in controlling inflationary pressure in Nigeria. Based on these findings, the study recommended that the Central Bank in collaboration with commercial banks should control inflation by keeping the interest rate at reasonable level in order to control inflation.

Abille & Mpuure (2020) conducted a study on the impact of monetary policy on controlling inflation in Ghana, using data from 1983 to 2017 and employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model for analysis. The findings revealed that the money supply had a positive and significant influence on inflation in the long run but exhibited a significant negative effect in the short run. Based on these results, it is recommended that policymakers focus on developing long-term strategies to stabilize the money supply growth rate, ensuring that increases align with economic output growth to prevent inflationary pressures. In the short term, monetary authorities should use tools like open market operations and reserve requirement adjustments to counteract inflationary spikes and stabilize prices. Strengthening Ghana's inflation-targeting framework through improved communication and transparency can help manage inflation expectations. Additionally, diversifying policy instruments, including interest rate adjustments and credit control measures, can provide flexibility in responding to inflation dynamics. Monitoring external factors such as global commodity prices and exchange rate fluctuations is crucial for mitigating the adverse effects of external shocks. Encouraging the use of advanced econometric models like ARDL for future policy analysis can lead to more informed and timely decisions. Public education about

inflation and monetary policy can also help align public expectations with policy objectives, enhancing policy effectiveness. By implementing these recommendations, Ghana can improve its monetary policy framework to control inflation effectively.

Theoretical Review:

This study is anchored on the Quantity Theory of Money (QTM), classically formulated by Irving Fisher (1911) in the equation of exchange, $MV = PY$. The theory posits a direct and proportional long-run relationship between the money supply (M) and the price level (P), implying that inflation is fundamentally a monetary phenomenon. This relationship rests on two critical assumptions: first, the velocity of money (V) is stable and determined by institutional factors; and second, real output (Y) is fixed in the short run at its full-employment level, determined by real factors like technology and resources.

The QTM provides the foundational rationale for this research. It justifies the use of monetary policy instruments like the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LR), and Open Market Operations (OMO), which are designed to control the money supply. By the logic of the QTM, controlling 'M' should directly and predictably control inflation 'P'. Therefore, this theory forms the core theoretical basis for expecting that the Central Bank of Nigeria's manipulation of these instruments should be effective in achieving its primary mandate of price stability.

Gaps in Literature

From the several studies reviewed none of these studies review up to 2024, therefore this study extends the period to 2024 in order to capture current effect of monetary instruments on inflation in Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed used/adopted Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and multiple regression models, with a few employing Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) models... Very few studies utilized the Vector Autoregressive Model (VAR). This study, however, employs the VAR model, allowing us to investigate models where variables are stationary at different levels.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted an ex-post facto research design to examine the impact of monetary policy on inflation without manipulating any variables. This design is appropriate because it analyzes historical data from 1993 to 2024 to identify patterns and potential causal relationships. Since direct experiments on monetary policy cannot be performed due to their respective ethical, practical, and economics constrains, this study used secondary data that basically emanated from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), national statistics, and financial institutions.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study is based on the Quantity Theory of Money developed by Fisher (1911). The equation shows a positive relationship between price level and money supply and can be represented using the quantity equation $MV=PY$. Based on this theory in an economy, money supply and price level will have a proportionate relationship. This means that if money supply increase by certain percentage, price level is also expected to increase by the same percentage. Ordinarily, it means that expansion in money supply leads to inflation.

Model Specification

The study adopted the model of Chinaemerem & Akujuobi (2012). Their model is given as: $INF = f(SM, P, CRR)$. above was adapted and Modified to capture the current variables in the study, by modifying the variables to include Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LR), and Open Market Operations (OMO), which are more direct instruments for the Nigerian context.

Justification of Methods

VAR models enable the simultaneous analysis of multiple interrelated time series variables, capturing dynamic interactions where each variable can act as both predictor and response. This is especially valuable in macroeconomics, where variables like GDP, inflation, and unemployment influence one another. VAR models are versatile for forecasting, as they reflect interdependencies and feedback effects, providing more accurate predictions for policy and planning.

RESULTS

The study conducted comprehensive econometric tests on the dataset covering 1993–2024, including unit root tests, Johansen co-integration, Granger causality, VAR estimation, impulse response analysis, and variance decomposition.

Unit Root Test

Table 1 Tabular presentation of ADF result

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Variables	ADF Statistics	p-value	Critical values			Order of integration
			1%	5%	10%	
INFLR	-8.446371	0.0000	-4.323979	-3.580622	-3.225334	I(1)
CRR	-6.942726	0.0042	-4.296729	-3.568379	-3.218382	I(1)
LRR	-6.482431	0.0000	-4.296729	-3.568379	-3.218382	I(1)
MPR	-6.213852	0.0001	-4.296729	-3.568379	-3.218382	I(1)
OMO	-8.154181	0.0020	-4.296729	-3.568379	-3.218382	I(1)

Source: Author’s computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

The Table 1 above presents the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root tests conducted on the variables under study. According to the decision rules, if the computed ADF test statistic is more negative than the critical values at 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, or if the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis of non-stationarity (presence of a unit root) is rejected.

From the results, all variables Inflation Rate (INFLR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Reserve Rate (LRR), Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), and Open Market Operations (OMO) have ADF statistics that are more negative than the critical values at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, and their p-values are all below the 0.05 threshold. This indicates that the null hypothesis of non-stationarity is rejected for all variables.

The order of integration for all variables is determined to be I(1), meaning they are stationary after the first difference. Hence, the variables are integrated of order one.

Given that the series are stationary at first difference, the study can confidently proceed to apply econometric models that require stationary data at I(1), such as the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model, to estimate and analyze the dynamic relationship among the variables in the operational model of this study.

Table 2: Vector Autoregression Results for Inflation Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
INFLR(-1)	0.339182	0.18772	1.80686	0.083
MPR(-1)	0.264780	0.89927	0.29444	0.770
CRR(-1)	0.707084	0.75262	0.93950	0.356
LRR(-1)	-0.113704	0.18941	-0.60030	0.553
OMO(-1)	-0.077760	0.08739	-0.88977	0.381
C	16.11591	17.6802	0.91152	0.369
R-squared	0.311			
Adj. R-squared	0.173			
F-statistic	2.259			

Source: Author’s computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

This table presents the core findings of the study, estimating the impact of monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria. The results clearly show that the lagged values of all four policy tools Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Reserve Ratio (LRR), and Open Market Operations (OMO) are statistically insignificant, as evidenced by their high p-values (all > 0.05) and low t-statistics. This indicates that past changes in these instruments have no statistically discernible effect on

the current inflation rate. Furthermore, the low R-squared value of 0.311 reveals that the model explains only about 31% of the variation in inflation, suggesting that the majority of inflationary dynamics are driven by factors outside this monetary policy framework, such as supply-side shocks or structural issues.

Table 3 Lag Length Criteria Result

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-561.1319	NA	6.22e+10	39.04358	39.27932	39.11741
1	-488.3672	115.4198*	2.38e+09*	35.74947*	37.16391*	36.19245*
2	-470.3846	22.32327	4.57e+09	36.23342	38.82657	37.04556
3	-457.4281	11.61622	1.72e+10	37.06400	40.83585	38.24530

Source: Author’s computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

From the table 3 above, it shows that all the lag order selection criteria indicate that lag one should be selected. This is because the values for the sequential modified Likelihood Ratio (LR) test statistic, Final Prediction Error (FPE), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SC), and Hannan Quinn Information Criterion (HQ) all attain their lowest values at lag one, as denoted by the asterisks (*). The decision rule for selecting the appropriate lag length is to choose the lag with the minimum values of these criteria, as this suggests a better model fit. Therefore, this study adopts lag one as the optimal lag length for the subsequent Vector Autoregression (VAR) estimation.

Co-integration Test Result

This analysis is used to ascertain long run relationship between explanatory variables and the explained variable. The test contains Trace statistics and Eigen value statistics. The decision will base on the number of co-integration equation indicated by these statistics.

Table 4: Johansen Co-integration test Base on Trace Statistics

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.913032	135.0254	79.34145	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.643440	64.20114	55.24578	0.0066
At most 2	0.547232	34.29480	35.01090	0.0596
At most 3	0.321483	11.31588	18.39771	0.3626
At most 4	0.002355	0.068375	3.841465	0.7937

Source: Author’s computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

The Johansen co-integration trace statistics in Table 4 indicate two co-integrating equations at the 5% significance level. The trace values for “None” (135.03) and “At most 1” (64.20) exceed their critical values (79.34 and 55.25) with p-values below 0.05, confirming a long-run relationship among the variables. However, the test for “At most 2” falls short of significance, supporting co-integration only up to the second rank.

Table 5: Johansen Co-integration test Based on Max- Eigen value Statistics

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.913032	70.82428	37.16359	0.0000
At most 1	0.643440	29.90634	30.81507	0.0643
At most 2	0.547232	22.97891	24.25202	0.0730
At most 3	0.321483	11.24751	17.14769	0.2927
At most 4	0.002355	0.068375	3.841465	0.7937

Source: Author’s computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

Table 5 above represents the Johansen co-integration test based on Max-Eigen statistics, and the result shows one (1) co-integration equation. Since only one (1) Max-Eigen statistic is greater than the critical value at the 5% level of significance, the study therefore rejects the null hypothesis (H_0) at that level and concludes that there exists a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables under study.

Table 6: Granger Causality Test Results

Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Probability	Decision
MPR does not Granger Cause INFLR	0.85300	0.3636	Accept H_0
CRR does not Granger Cause INFLR	0.15216	0.6994	Accept H_0
LRR does not Granger Cause INFLR	0.07578	0.7851	Accept H_0
OMO does not Granger Cause INFLR	0.06399	0.8021	Accept H_0
INFLR does not Granger Cause MPR	0.57787	0.4535	Accept H_0

Source: Author's computation 2024, using E-views 12.0 version

The Granger causality tests investigate the predictive relationship between the variables. The results confirm a critical finding: none of the monetary policy instruments Granger-cause inflation. The high probability values (all > 0.35) for the null hypotheses (e.g., "MPR does not Granger Cause INFLR") lead us to accept them, meaning that past values of MPR, CRR, LRR, and OMO do not contain useful information for forecasting future inflation. This lack of predictive power reinforces the conclusion from the VAR model, indicating a broken or ineffective transmission mechanism from monetary policy actions to price levels in the Nigerian economy.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results indicate that the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) has a positive but statistically insignificant impact on inflation at the 5% significance level (t-statistic = 0.294, p-value = 0.770), suggesting that interest rate adjustments alone are ineffective for controlling inflation in Nigeria. This ineffectiveness is attributed to structural weaknesses such as a highly informal economy, excess liquidity within the banking system, and persistent supply-side inflationary pressures including food and fuel price shocks. This finding aligns with Nuhu and Odiba (2021) but contrasts with evidence from advanced economies (Mishkin, 2016), where interest rate tools are a primary lever for inflation control.

Similarly, the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) also exhibits a positive yet statistically insignificant relationship with inflation (t-statistic = 0.940, p-value = 0.356). This indicates a reduced effectiveness of reserve requirements in the Nigerian context, likely due to high currency circulation outside the banking system and persistent government borrowing from the central bank, which injects liquidity that offsets the contractionary intent of CRR adjustments. This finding supports Akindutire, Ajayi, and Yusuf (2019) on the diminishing potency of the CRR but differs from Bakare (2011), who found it impactful in earlier periods with a less complex economic structure.

Furthermore, the Liquidity Ratio (LR) shows no significant effect on inflation (t-statistic = -0.600, p-value = 0.553). This result reflects the reality of Nigeria's banking system, where lenders often maintain voluntary excess liquidity due to a lack of viable lending opportunities, while high-yielding government securities crowd out credit to the productive private sector. This aligns with the conclusions of Danjuma et al. (2012) but contrasts with Okotori (2019), who found more modest effects.

Lastly, Open Market Operations (OMO) are also statistically insignificant (t-statistic = -0.890, p-value = 0.381), indicating a limited independent capacity for inflation control. This is consistent with Adebayo et al. (2023), who noted that OMO's effectiveness in Nigeria is often contingent on being paired with foreign exchange stability measures. This finding, however, differs from Bonga-Bonga (2017), who found OMO to be effective in controlling inflation within South Africa's deeper and more developed financial markets.

CONCLUSION

The study arrives at a nuanced conclusion regarding the effect of monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria. The core finding from the short-run Vector Autoregression (VAR) analysis is that the individual monetary policy instruments Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR), Liquidity Ratio (LR), and Open Market Operations (OMO) did not exert a statistically significant impact on inflation during the study period. This points to a severely weakened and ineffective monetary policy transmission mechanism in the short run.

However, this finding is critically qualified by the results of the Johansen co-integration test, which confirmed the existence of a significant long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. This implies that, despite their short-run ineffectiveness, monetary policy instruments and inflation are bound together in a stable relationship over the long term, consistent with fundamental economic theory.

The stark disconnect between the insignificant short-run results and the significant long-run relationship is explained by deep-rooted structural and institutional challenges. These constraints include a large informal sector, persistent excess liquidity in the banking system, supply-side inflation drivers such as food and energy price shocks, and fiscal dominance that often undermines monetary policy efforts. These factors disrupt the short-term transmission of policy signals while the underlying long-term relationship predicted by theory ultimately holds.

Therefore, the study underscores that achieving price stability in Nigeria requires a dual-strategy approach. Policymakers must work to revitalize the short-term transmission mechanism by deepening financial markets, enhancing financial inclusion, and ensuring better fiscal-monetary coordination. Simultaneously, they must recognize that monetary policy alone is insufficient and must be complemented by robust structural reforms aimed at improving agricultural productivity, addressing infrastructural deficits, and stabilizing the exchange rate. This integrated approach is essential to bridge the gap between the long-run potential and short-run ineffectiveness of monetary policy for sustainable inflation management and macroeconomic stability in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The main focus of this research is to examine the impact of monetary policy instruments on inflation in Nigeria using the Vector Autoregression (VAR) model. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The estimated VAR model reveals that the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) has a positive but statistically insignificant impact on inflation in Nigeria. Therefore, it is recommended that policymakers should not rely solely on MPR as a tool for inflation control. Instead, they should strengthen financial inclusion and formal sector participation to enhance the transmission of interest rate policy.
- ii. Also, the VAR model reveals that the coefficient of the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) is positive but statistically insignificant. Therefore, it is recommended that the Central Bank of Nigeria should consider complementing CRR adjustments with structural reforms such as reducing cash-based transactions, promoting digital banking, and discouraging excessive government borrowing that undermines CRR effectiveness.
- iii. Similarly, the estimated VAR model reveals that the coefficient of the Liquidity Ratio (LRR) is statistically insignificant. Therefore, it is recommended that policymakers should re-evaluate the design and enforcement of liquidity regulations and consider introducing differentiated reserve requirements that target specific sectors to improve credit allocation and inflation responsiveness.
- iv. Finally, the VAR model reveals that the coefficient of Open Market Operations (OMO) is statistically insignificant in influencing inflation. Therefore, it is recommended that the Central Bank should deepen Nigeria's financial markets by improving government securities infrastructure, strengthening market-making mechanisms, and ensuring better coordination between OMO activities and foreign exchange policy for improved inflation control.

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